

Perspectives and Practices of Inner Source Contributors

Definition: Inner Source is the application of Open Source approach within the corporate environment.

- (1) Inner Source leverages practices from open source development.
- (2) Contrary to open source, only a limited group of developers (employees of a specific organization/company) can take part in the community.

The software product or component that is developed within an Inner Source context is called Inner Source Software. The source code of inner source software is open and visible for everyone within the organization/company.

*Required

Demographics

1. What is your year of birth? *

2. What is your gender? *

Mark only one oval.

Female

Male

Prefer not to say

Other: _____

3. What is your current occupation? *

Mark only one oval.

Industrial or freelance professional

Academic or industrial researcher

Undergraduate/graduate student

Other: _____

4. How long have you been with your current company/organization? (in years, decimals okay)

*

5. Which of the following best describes your primary job role? *

Mark only one oval.

Development

Testing

Project Management

Other: _____

6. About how many years of experience do you have with your primary job role? (Please input a number, decimals okay) *

7. Current country/area of residence?

Mark only one oval.

- Afghanistan (AFG)
- Albania (ALB)
- Algeria (DZA)
- American Samoa (ASM)
- Andorra (AND)
- Angola (AGO)
- Anguilla (AIA)
- Antigua and Barbuda (ATG)
- Argentina (ARG)
- Armenia (ARM)
- Aruba (ABW)
- Australia (AUS)
- Austria (AUT)
- Azerbaijan (AZE)
- Bahamas, The (BHM)
- Bahrain (BHR)
- Bangladesh (BGD)
- Barbados (BRB)
- Belarus (BLR)
- Belgium (BEL)
- Belize (BLZ)
- Benin (BEN)
- Bermuda (BMU)
- Bhutan (BTN)
- Bolivia (BOL)
- Bosnia and Herzegovina (BIH)
- Botswana (BWA)
- Brazil (BRA)
- British Virgin Islands (VGB)
- Brunei (BRN)
- Bulgaria (BGR)
- Burkina Faso (BFA)
- Burma (MMR)
- Burundi (BDI)
- Cabo Verde (CPV)
- Cambodia (KHM)

- Cameroon (CMR)
- Canada (CAN)
- Cayman Islands (CYM)
- Central African Republic (CAF)
- Chad (TCD)
- Chile (CHL)
- China (CHN)
- Colombia (COL)
- Comoros (COM)
- Congo, Democratic Republic of the (COD)
- Congo, Republic of the (COG)
- Cook Islands (COK)
- Costa Rica (CRI)
- Cote d'Ivoire (CIV)
- Croatia (HRV)
- Cuba (CUB)
- Curacao (CUW)
- Cyprus (CYP)
- Czech Republic (CZE)
- Denmark (DNK)
- Djibouti (DJI)
- Dominica (DMA)
- Dominican Republic (DOM)
- Ecuador (ECU)
- Egypt (EGY)
- El Salvador (SLV)
- Equatorial Guinea (GNQ)
- Eritrea (ERI)
- Estonia (EST)
- Ethiopia (ETH)
- Falkland Islands (Islas Malvinas) (FLK)
- Faroe Islands (FRO)
- Fiji (FJI)
- Finland (FIN)
- France (FRA)
- French Polynesia (PYF)
- Gabon (GAB)
- Gambia, The (GMB)
- Georgia (GEO)

- Germany (DEU)
- Ghana (GHA)
- Gibraltar (GIB)
- Greece (GRC)
- Greenland (GRL)
- Grenada (GRD)
- Guam (GUM)
- Guatemala (GTM)
- Guernsey (GGY)
- Guinea-Bissau (GNB)
- Guinea (GIN)
- Guyana (GUY)
- Haiti (HTI)
- Honduras (HND)
- Hong Kong (HKG)
- Hungary (HUN)
- Iceland (ISL)
- India (IND)
- Indonesia (IDN)
- Iran (IRN)
- Iraq (IRQ)
- Ireland (IRL)
- Isle of Man (IMN)
- Israel (ISR)
- Italy (ITA)
- Jamaica (JAM)
- Japan (JPN)
- Jersey (JEY)
- Jordan (JOR)
- Kazakhstan (KAZ)
- Kenya (KEN)
- Kiribati (KIR)
- Korea, North (PRK)
- Korea, South (KOR)
- Kosovo (KSV)
- Kuwait (KWT)
- Kyrgyzstan (KGZ)
- Laos (LAO)
- Latvia (LVA)

- Lebanon (LBN)
- Lesotho (LSO)
- Liberia (LBR)
- Libya (LBY)
- Liechtenstein (LIE)
- Lithuania (LTU)
- Luxembourg (LUX)
- Macau (MAC)
- Macedonia (MKD)
- Madagascar (MDG)
- Malawi (MWI)
- Malaysia (MYS)
- Maldives (MDV)
- Mali (MLI)
- Malta (MLT)
- Marshall Islands (MHL)
- Mauritania (MRT)
- Mauritius (MUS)
- Mexico (MEX)
- Micronesia, Federated States of (FSM)
- Moldova (MDA)
- Monaco (MCO)
- Mongolia (MNG)
- Montenegro (MNE)
- Morocco (MAR)
- Mozambique (MOZ)
- Namibia (NAM)
- Nepal (NPL)
- Netherlands (NLD)
- New Caledonia (NCL)
- New Zealand (NZL)
- Nicaragua (NIC)
- Nigeria (NGA)
- Niger (NER)
- Niue (NIU)
- Northern Mariana Islands (MNP)
- Norway (NOR)
- Oman (OMN)
- Pakistan (PAK)

- Palau (PLW)
- Panama (PAN)
- Papua New Guinea (PNG)
- Paraguay (PRY)
- Peru (PER)
- Philippines (PHL)
- Poland (POL)
- Portugal (PRT)
- Puerto Rico (PRI)
- Qatar (QAT)
- Romania (ROU)
- Russia (RUS)
- Rwanda (RWA)
- Saint Kitts and Nevis (KNA)
- Saint Lucia (LCA)
- Saint Martin (MAF)
- Saint Pierre and Miquelon (SPM)
- Saint Vincent and the Grenadines (VCT)
- Samoa (WSM)
- San Marino (SMR)
- Sao Tome and Principe (STP)
- Saudi Arabia (SAU)
- Senegal (SEN)
- Serbia (SRB)
- Seychelles (SYC)
- Sierra Leone (SLE)
- Singapore (SGP)
- Sint Maarten (SXM)
- Slovakia (SVK)
- Slovenia (SVN)
- Solomon Islands (SLB)
- Somalia (SOM)
- South Africa (ZAF)
- South Sudan (SSD)
- Spain (ESP)
- Sri Lanka (LKA)
- Sudan (SDN)
- Suriname (SUR)
- Swaziland (SWZ)

- Sweden (SWE)
- Switzerland (CHE)
- Syria (SYR)
- Taiwan (TWN)
- Tajikistan (TJK)
- Tanzania (TZA)
- Thailand (THA)
- Timor-Leste (TLS)
- Togo (TGO)
- Tonga (TON)
- Trinidad and Tobago (TTO)
- Tunisia (TUN)
- Turkey (TUR)
- Turkmenistan (TKM)
- Tuvalu (TUV)
- Uganda (UGA)
- Ukraine (UKR)
- United Arab Emirates (ARE)
- United Kingdom (GBR)
- United States (USA)
- Uruguay (URY)
- Uzbekistan (UZB)
- Vanuatu (VUT)
- Venezuela (VEN)
- Vietnam (VNM)
- Virgin Islands (VGB)
- West Bank (WBG)
- Yemen (YEM)
- Zambia (ZMB)
- Zimbabwe (ZWE)

8. Your primary programming language? *

Mark only one oval.

- C/C++
- C#
- Go
- Java
- JavaScript
- Kotlin
- Objective-C
- Perl
- PHP
- Python
- R
- Ruby
- Rust
- Scala
- SQL
- Swift
- TypeScript
- Visual Basic
- Other: _____

9. Have you contributed to open source project(s)? *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No

10. Have you contributed to inner source projects(s)? *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No

11. Do you receive extra pay beyond your salary for your contribution to inner-source project(s)? *

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

12. How many inner source projects do you participate in? (A number) *

Please answer the following questions based on your experience with the primary inner source project to which you contribute:

13. What best describes the object of the primary inner source project you contribute to? *

Mark only one oval.

Exploration oriented: the project aims to make innovation accessible to the inner source community.

Utility oriented: the project aims to fill an immediate need in functionality.

Service oriented: the project aims to provide stable and robust services to end users of the inner source software.

Other: _____

14. About how many contributors exist in your primary inner source project? *

Mark only one oval.

1-5

6-10

11-20

21-40

Other: _____

15. How is your primary inner source project governed? *

Mark only one oval.

- Governed by one single organizational unit
- Governed by a board formed of multiple organizational units
- Shared between all organizational units in the organization/company
- Other: _____

What best describes the role(s) you play in your primary inner source project?

16. (1) Project-centric roles (please select all that apply): *

Tick all that apply.

- Coder: I develop new code, maintain existing code, and write tests.
- Project Manager: I do project managing, in budget, on time and on schedule.
- System Admin: I provide technical support and system administration.
- Other: _____

17. (2) Community-Centric (please select all that apply): *

Tick all that apply.

- Founder: I create the project.
- Advocate: I bring new people in.
- Mentor: I train newcomers.
- Strategist: I understand and control the quality of processes.
- Treasurer: I lead strategic budgetary decisions.
- Writer: I write documentation.
- Other: _____

18. About how many years have you been working on your primary inner source project?
(Please input a number, decimals okay) *

19. How much time per week do you spend contributing to your primary inner source project? *

Mark only one oval.

- Less than 5 hours/week
- From 5 to 10 hours/week
- From 10 to 20 hours/week
- More than 20 hours/week

20. Please kindly assess your level of satisfaction with the following aspects based on your experience with your primary inner source project: *

Mark only one oval per row.

	Very Dissatisfied	Dissatisfied	Neutral	Satisfied	Very Satisfied	I don't understand.
Communication	<input type="radio"/>					
Working Atmosphere	<input type="radio"/>					
Recognition	<input type="radio"/>					
Outcomes	<input type="radio"/>					

21. Please kindly rate each statement as below: *

Mark only one oval per row.

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree	I don't understand.
I plan to continue contributing to this project in the future.	<input type="radio"/>					
I look forward to being involved in inner source development in the future.	<input type="radio"/>					

Inner Source:
Motivations

Please kindly rate each statement as below based on your experience with your primary inner source project.

(1) Extrinsic Motivations

22. I contribute to the inner source project because: *

Mark only one oval per row.

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree	I don't understand.
Inner source enhances my expertise for my career development.	<input type="radio"/>					
My manager/leader supports my contribution to inner source.	<input type="radio"/>					
Contributing to inner source is my job responsibility.	<input type="radio"/>					

(2) Intrinsic Motivations

23. I contribute to the inner source project because: *

Mark only one oval per row.

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree	I don't understand.
Adoption of inner source can benefit my company/organization.	<input type="radio"/>					
I enjoy helping others if I can.	<input type="radio"/>					
Inner source helps me share software and knowledge.	<input type="radio"/>					
I feel good when I belong to a certain group of people.	<input type="radio"/>					
I enjoy the fun when I contribute to inner source projects.	<input type="radio"/>					

(3) Internalized Extrinsic Motivations

24. I contribute to the inner source project because: *

Mark only one oval per row.

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree	I don't understand.
Inner source gives me an opportunity to learn new things.	<input type="radio"/>					
Inner source community provides feedback to improve my software.	<input type="radio"/>					
Inner source provides me with a means of learning from others.	<input type="radio"/>					
I would like to create required but unavailable features/software.	<input type="radio"/>					
Inner source helps me build up my reputation as an expert.	<input type="radio"/>					
Inner source helps me expand my professional network with colleagues.	<input type="radio"/>					

25. (Optional) What are other motives that motivate you to contribute to inner source projects?

This content is neither created nor endorsed by Google.

Google Forms